
Network medicine might lead to new treatments for dyslipidemia. It will be a challenging method to implement in a clinical context

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Abstract: With statin-based therapies to prevent or delay atherosclerotic progression, the reductionist approach of strict guidelines for treating dyslipidemias resulted in remarkable low-density lipoprotein transported cholesterol reduction. The precise estimation of residual cardiovascular diseases risk, on the other hand, remains a significant challenge that necessitates the development of new integrated approaches. The application of a network medicine approach could lead to the development of novel strategies. This is unquestionably a multidisciplinary strategy that will be difficult to put into practice in a clinical setting. We must dissect a patient with dyslipidemia to the level of single cell analysis and then reconstruct the puzzle to get a complete picture of nodes and disease modules. These efforts are critical for fully comprehending the molecular networks that underpin dyslipidemia and atherosclerosis. Furthermore, computer-aided decision-making is becoming more common in the clinical evaluation of subjects with suspected coronary heart disease. Physicians, on the other hand, should keep in mind that machines lack a "sense of reasoning" and should therefore question the reliability of a clinical decision made solely by robots. As a result, AI should be referred to as "augmented intelligence," which can aid physicians in decision-making but should leave the final strategy in their hands.

1. Introduction

In humans, atherosclerosis begins at a young age (de Nigris et al., 2018; Napoli et al., 1997, 1999). It is the formation of fatty streak lesions in unstable plaque within the artery wall as a result of high circulating cholesterol levels, and it is one of the leading causes of cardiovascular death (Libby et al., 2019; Ross, 1999). Dyslipidemias, according to the European Society of Cardiology's (ESC) new guidelines (ESC Committee for Practice Guidelines (CPG), 2019), are an independent and modifiable risk factor for the onset and progression of coronary heart disease (CHD). Modifiable risk factors, such as diet, smoking, and physical activity, are classified as such, as are nonmodifiable risk factors, such as age, gender, and individual genetic variations associated with loci regulating serum lipid levels (de Nigris et al., 2018; Libby et al., 2019). Dyslipidemias are heterogeneous at the molecular level, ranging from rare monogenic dyslipidemias (e.g., Familial Hypercholesterolemia, FH) to common high-complex polygenic syndromes involving hundreds of genes (Berberich and Hegele, 2019). Dyslipidemias are characterized by lipidome abnormalities that include: (1) elevated plasma levels of total cholesterol, low-density lipoprotein transported cholesterol (LDLC), and triacylglycerols (TAG); (2) decreased plasma levels of high-density lipoprotein transported cholesterol (HDLC); and (3) concomitant elevation of LDLC, TAG, and reduction of HDLC (Brautbar et al., 2011). Rare genetic mutations or common single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) cause upregulation or defective clearance of LDL-C and TAG levels (eg, FH), as well as downregulation or excessive clearance of HDL-C, resulting in primary

dyslipidemias (Berberich and Hegele, 2019). Hyperglycemia, hypothyroidism, liver dysfunction, chronic kidney disease (CKD), and pharmacological therapies, such as antihypertensive and immunosuppressive drugs, are also linked to secondary dyslipidemias (Vodnala et al., 2012). Despite advances in our understanding of lipidome-related molecular perturbations in early and late life (de Nigris et al., 2018; Napoli et al., 1997, 1999), current risk assessment and pharmacological management of dyslipidemias are inadequate (Costa et al., 2019; Scognamiglio et al., 2019). Thus, novel molecular pathways linking genotype and phenotype that could be regulated by epigenetic mechanisms could explain why common drugs like statins or niacin do not completely normalize the lipidome profile in these patients (Bonetti et al., 2003; Marfella et al., 2020; Palinski and Napoli, 2002; Zhao et al., 2014, Napoli C, 2012, Napoli C, 2006). By blocking HDLC's anti-atherogenic effects, a pioneering study demonstrated that a novel rare mutation causing higher levels of HDLC is associated with an increased risk of CV events (Zanoni et al., 2016). This could explain why a large randomized trial using niacin (NCT00461630) failed to achieve beneficial therapeutic effects in increasing HDL-C levels. Nonetheless, in order to develop personalized therapy, novel molecular networks underlying metabolic reprogramming in atherosclerosis must be identified (Benincasa et al., 2020; Infante et al., 2020). The Network Medicine approach is based on a multidisciplinary clinical strategy that connects the molecular basis of complex diseases with phenotypic/clinical data by combining innovative omic platforms, bioinformatic algorithms, imaging techniques, and artificial intelligence (AI) to aid physician decision-making (Benincasa et al., 2020; Infante et al., 2020).

Dyslipidemia and atherosclerosis are treated using a network medicine approach. A network medicine approach is comprised of three critical components: (1) defining molecular pathways underlying key endophenotypes using powerful bioinformatic network-oriented algorithms; (2) integrating multiple omics data to obtain overall information about perturbations of the cardiac interactome at the single-patient level using tissue biopsy and liquid-based assays; and (3) combining clinical aBy improving precision medicine and personalized therapy, this integrated clinical approach aims to create a networked map that can be used to predict, diagnose, and monitor CV diseases. DIAMOnD, degreeaware disease gene prioritization; EHR, electronic health records; FAI, fat adipose index; GenePanda, gene prioritizing approach using network distance analyses; LDLC, low-density lipoprotein transported cholesterol; MMInetwork, MiRNAMediated interactions network; PRINCE, PRIoritization and Complex Elucidation; POCT, point of care testing; ProDiGe, Prioritization of Disease WGCNA is an acronym for weighted correlation network analysis.

2. Current Approaches to Dyslipidemia Risk Stratification and Treatment

The easy-to-use Systematic COronary Risk Evaluation (SCORE) algorithm is recommended by current ESC guidelines (ESC Committee for Practice Guidelines (CPG), 2019) to estimate the short-term (10 years) risk of CV death. The SCORE chart is calibrated for several countries and is calculated as a function of age, gender, systolic blood pressure, smoking status, and total cholesterol level to assist physicians in making lifestyle recommendations and treatment decisions. Statins are now the gold standard for primary and secondary prevention of dyslipidemia, lowering LDL levels by 30% to 50% in both men and women (ESC Committee for Practice Guidelines (CPG), 2019). Lipid lowering therapy is recommended for patients who fall into one of the following categories: (1) very high risk (diabetes with organ injury, CKD with GFR 30 mL/min/m², or a SCORE 10%); (2) high risk (diabetics, CKD with GFR 30–60 mL/min/m², or a SCORE 5–10 percent), if LDLC 70 mg/dL; and (3) moderate risk (SCORE 10-year risk of coronary mortality 1–5%), if Adjunct

treatments include significant dietary and lifestyle changes (Piepoli et al., 2016). Surprisingly, even in the absence of CV events, FH patients should be treated with lipid-lowering agents to prevent or at least delay cardiac damage (Casula et al., 2018). FH diagnosis is sometimes made only after patients exhibit clinical signs and/or atherosclerotic events at a young age (EAS Familial Hypercholesterolaemia Studies Collaboration et al., 2018).

We present a list of completed phase III and IV clinical trials with published results from the website <https://clinicaltrials.gov> in the last ten years (Bhatt et al., 2019; Chen et al., 2019; Davidson et al., 2012; Ferdinand et al., 2012; Giugliano et al., 2017; Golomb et al., 2015; Ridker et al., 2018; Sabatine et al., 2017). In addition, major ongoing clinical trials are investigating the efficacy of diet supplementation with natural compounds (red yeast rice, phytosterols, betaglucan, berberine, and probiotics) (Becker et al., 2013; Chau et al., 2019; Crescenti et al., 2013; Mannarino et al., 2009; Solà et al., 2014).

The Potential of Network Medicine in Precision Medicine and Personalized Therapy for Cardiovascular Diseases

Barabasi (Barabási, 2007) coined the term "Network Medicine" to emphasize how the universal law of networks can be translated into clinical practice to improve precision medicine for complex diseases. A network is made up of nodes (genes or proteins) that are connected in pairs by lines (edges) if there is a functional relationship between them (Benincasa et al., 2019a, b, 2020; Infante et al., 2020; Menche et al., 2015; Napoli et al., 2019, 2020). Network Medicine is a molecular bioengineering approach that combines clinical data with heterogeneous omics findings (genome, transcriptome, proteome, epigenome, metabolome, microbiome, exposome, and foodome) to provide mechanistic understanding and reclassification of complex diseases (Benincasa et al., 2019a, b, 2020; Infante et al., 2020; Menche et al., 2015; Napoli et al., 2019, 2020). Gene Prioritizing Approach Using Network Distance Analyses (GenePanda), DegreeAware Disease Gene Prioritization (DIAMOnD), Prioritization Of Disease Genes (ProDiGe), and Weighted Correlation Network A are some of the quantitative platforms that can be used to identify disease specific network modules containing a set of interacting genes potentially involved in disease pathogenesis (Benincasa et al., 2019a, b, 2020; Infante et al., 2020; Menche et al., 2015; Napoli et al., 2019, 2020).

Systems pharmacology (or polypharmacology) is a branch of Network Medicine that focuses on: (1) identifying key molecular networks whose perturbation has desirable clinical effects, (2) computer-aided design of novel drugs that target entire molecular networks rather than single proteins (multitarget drugs, MTD), and (3) identification of protein–protein interactions (PPI) (Casas et al., 2019; Cheng et al., 2018; Stroik et al., 2018).

Primary Prevention of Dyslipidemias and Atherosclerosis Using Network-Oriented Analysis

A map of dyslipidemia-related molecular mechanisms could help researchers better understand how atherosclerosis develops in individuals. Table 1 summarizes the most recent studies that used integrated network-oriented analysis to identify potential risk biomarkers and drug targets (Adiels et al., 2018; Chen et al., 2014; Miao et al., 2019; Wang and Loscalzo, 2018; Yao et al., 2015; Ye et al., 2013). A networked map to help physicians and patients with personalized dyslipidemia therapy. The main current results from the network medicine approach in treating patients with dyslipidemia to prevent and reduce the burden of atherosclerosis are depicted in this diagram.

A coexpression network of differentially expressed (DE) transcripts was built using available microarray datasets from T cells and monocytes isolated from FH patients. The investigation uncovered a number of gene pairs involved in cholesterol lipoprotein metabolism that had been disrupted (Ye et al., 2013). Chronic myeloid leukemia, the neurotrophin signaling pathway, and SNARE protein interactions in vesicular transport have all been identified as key deregulated signaling pathways in FH, according to a GO analysis (Ye et al., 2013). Another microarray platform used on circulating monocytes discovered a map of 443 DE transcripts that could be used to differentiate FH patients from healthy controls (Chen et al., 2014). The authors created two FH regulatory maps that focused on interactions between transcription factors (TF) and gene targets, as well as interactions between microRNA (miRNA) and their target genes, revealing key pathways linked to FH pathobiology (Chen et al., 2014). As a result, bloodbased tests may shed light on the disrupted molecular networks that aid in the early diagnosis of FH patients. Changes in the collagen type 1 alpha 1 chain (COL1A1) gene expression may increase TAG levels in obese subjects, leading to dyslipidemia, according to another study that used the WGCNA algorithm to analyze available GEO microarray data (Miao et al., 2019). Furthermore, downstream analysis revealed that elevated levels of circulating miR3659, which can target SNP in the COL1A1 3'untranslated regions (UTR), could be a biomarker for dyslipidemias in obese patients with metabolic syndrome (Miao et al., 2019). To confirm the clinical significance of these findings, larger population studies and multicenter trials are required.

Treatment of Dyslipidemias and Primary Prevention of Atherosclerosis Using Network Oriented Analysis

Seed Connector algorithm (SCA), a novel network-based algorithm, was applied to CHD-related seed proteins, revealing novel biological intermediaries (seed connectors) related to LDL cholesterol, TAG-rich lipoproteins, inflammation, cellular proliferation, vascular remodeling, and nitric oxide (Wang and Loscalzo, 2018). Interestingly, the antiangiogenic agent pegaptanib targets neuropilin1 (NRP1), which resulted in a new seed connector in the CHD network, suggesting a possible repurposing for atherosclerotic disease management (Wang and Loscalzo, 2018). Monotherapy with extended-release (ER) niacin can normalize the plasma lipid and apolipoprotein profile, with changes in TAG and HDLC being particularly closely linked (Yao et al., 2015).

3. Secondary Preventative Measures

Genotyping and gene expression profiling were used to construct an SNPgene expression network using whole blood samples isolated from Framingham Heart Study participants. (Adiels and colleagues, 2018). A pleiotropic SNP (rs964184) in the ZPR1 zinc finger (ZNF259) gene was found to be cisassociated with the expression of the proprotein convertase subtilisin/kexin type 7 (PCSK7) gene, promoting interindividual variation in LDL, HDL, and TAG plasma levels, suggesting a new therapeutic target (Adiels et al., 2018).

4. Personalized Dyslipidemia Treatment with Artificial Intelligence

As the first-line noninvasive imaging test, coronary CT angiography (CCTA) has progressed to a more detailed characterization of the coronary wall and perivascular region (Antonopoulos et al., 2017; Oikonomou et al., 2019a). A novel biomarker called Fat Attenuation Index (FAITM) has been established by using AI to quantify arterial inflammation from CCTA data (Antonopoulos et al., 2017; Oikonomou et al., 2019a). FAITM is a statin and PCSK9i-responsive measure of adipocyte lipid content (PVAT) that can detect plaque formation before coronary calcification or significant stenosis (Oikonomou et al.,

2018, 2019b). Furthermore, a machine learning algorithm has demonstrated a positive predictive value (0.85) in the detection of FH patients in the general population, stratifying the risk (Banda et al., 2019). A randomized trial consistently tested a Computerized Decision Support System (CDS), named HTEDLP, in the treatment of dyslipidemia by providing automatic specific reminders, a sequence of clinical decisions (eg, lipid-lowering therapy), and recommendations tailored to each patient (Zamora et al., 2013). HTEDLP was found to be comfortable and simple to use, with a significant reduction in LDLC levels in high-risk CV patients (Zamora et al., 2013). Larger cohort studies, however, are required to confirm these findings in clinical practice. Furthermore, the Niemann-Pick C1 (NPC1) protein folding as well as the response of different NPC1 genetic variants to SAHA treatment have been modeled using a machine learning approach (Wang et al., 2019). SAHA is an FDA-approved epigenetic drug that works as a histone deacetyltransferase inhibitor (HDACi), increasing Lys acetylation in specific NPC1 chain domains (Wang et al., 2019). Overall, this platform provided mechanistic findings in PPI that contribute to NPC1 disease, as well as predicted residues that are likely to respond to HDACi, which are commonly tested in clinical trials for major CV diseases (Schiano et al., 2020a).

5. Digital Therapeutics for Personalized Dyslipidemia Treatment

The impact of Digital Therapeutics (DTx) on customized therapy has been accelerated, as emphasized in the most recent IQVIA Institute Research report (<https://www.iqvia.com/>). This is due to the growing number of mobile health-based apps and wearable sensors that can assist patients and physicians in CV care (Beatty et al., 2013; Brooks et al., 2015). DTx is a software and technology combination that helps patients improve CV clinical outcomes (Beatty et al., 2013; Brooks et al., 2015). It must be evaluated based on five criteria: intended use, demonstrated efficacy, regulatory clearance, integration into standard of care, and demonstrated cost-effectiveness. The Canadian Cardiovascular Society (CCS) recently released a mobile app that lists the recommendations for managing dyslipidemia as a useful tool to aid physician decisions (Anderson et al., 2016).

In addition, the American College of Cardiology (ACC) developed the LDLC Manager (<https://www.acc.org/LDLcmanager.com>), a mobile app aimed at assisting physicians in lowering CHD risk through a personalized lipid-lowering process that relies on three tools: the ASCVD Risk Estimator, Statin Intolerance App, and The Lipid Lowering Therapy Pathway Tool. It is important to note that the information and recommendations provided in these apps are not intended to replace clinical evaluation; rather, they can help physicians make better decisions. There are also several point-of-care testing (POCT) options for cholesterol measurements (Plüddemann et al., 2012). Plüddemann et al. (2012) used the portable handheld Accutrend Plus, BeneCheck Plus, CardioChek PA, Cholestech LDX, and the compact desktop analyzer Cholestech LDX to measure lipid fractions and ratios in whole blood, plasma, or serum collected from the finger or venous blood. These tools still have a degree of variability due to the POCT device's imprecision.

6. Conclusion

The reductionist approach of strict guidelines for treating dyslipidemia resulted in remarkable LDLC reduction with statin-based therapies to prevent or delay atherosclerotic progression. However, precise estimation of residual CV risk remains a significant challenge that necessitates the development of novel integrated approaches (Schiano et al., 2020b, Napoli et al., 2012, Napoli et al., 2006). The use of a network medicine approach could result in novel strategies. This is undoubtedly a multidisciplinary strategy that will be difficult to implement

in a clinical setting. To obtain a complete picture of nodes and disease modules, we must dissect a patient with dyslipidemia to the level of single cell analysis and then reconstruct the puzzle. These efforts are critical for a complete understanding of the molecular networks that underpin dyslipidemia and atherosclerosis. Furthermore, in the clinical evaluation of subjects with suspected CHD, computer aided decision making is becoming more prevalent. Physicians, on the other hand, should keep in mind that machines lack a "sense of reasoning" and should therefore question the reliability of a solely robotic clinical decision. As a result, AI should be referred to as "augmented intelligence," which can assist physicians in making decisions but should leave the final strategy in the hands of the physician.

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